

A CAUSAL MODEL ON PERSONAL EFFECTIVENESS OF NON-COMMISSIONED OFFICERS IN RELATION TO PERCEIVED EMPOWERMENT, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ETHICAL LEADERSHIP OF COMMISSIONED OFFICERS IN THE PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to investigate the causal effect of ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence to the personal effectiveness of non-commissioned officers. A descriptive-causal research design was used to determine the level of variables, the relationship that naturally exists between and among them, and the impact of ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence to personal effectiveness. Four hundred police personnel were selected purposively and responded to the survey, and data were analyzed using the mean, Pearson product-moment correlation analysis, and path analysis. According to descriptive results, PNP non-commissioned officers were perceived to have a high level of personal effectiveness and the commissioned officers have high level of ethical leadership, and very high levels for empowerment and emotional intelligence. Regression-correlation revealed a scientifically significant positive relationships between exogenous variables and endogenous variable. Path analysis results showed that empowerment has no direct effect on personal effectiveness. But it has for ethical leadership and emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Criminal justice, personal effectiveness, ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, Philippine National Police, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal effectiveness is defined as how well a person can use all his resources such as energy, time, skills, and strength to achieve goals efficiently. It can be shown and exhibited in different ways such as values and priorities (McCrimmon, 2022). However, if left unaddressed, lack of personal effectiveness can create a vicious life that can affect professional life and, worst, it can leak into one's personal life and affect their work-life balance (Little, 2017). This research will contribute to the realization of Item Number 16 (Peace Justice and Strong Institutions) of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations as adapted by the Philippine government.

In the Philippine Law Enforcement field, it is reported that police officers' personal effectiveness uniquely holds them in being responsible for maintaining public peace, protection of properties, and safeguarding lives; however, if left unchecked, some authorities may initiate viciousness. Hence, lack of personal effectiveness may result to abuse of power that may affect to increasing offense scenes of violence, human rights abuses, and internal institutional issues (Adame, Perea & Manibo, 2019) and worst this may cause downward trend on public's confidence and trust on the police force (Mynenko, 2022).

The study of personal effectiveness is widely focused on the ability to demonstrate respect, dignity, and integrity in interpersonal relationships and to demonstrate positive personal coping and wellness strategies (University of Calgary, 2022). In the field of law enforcement, the effectiveness of a leaders is reflective of their managerial capabilities (Florendo, 2012). Moreover, past research shows that levels of both aspects of job-related well-being, job burnout and work engagement are related to work values and personal effectiveness to which values represents people's highest priorities and are cognitive representations of basic motivations (Basinka & Daderman, 2019).

In the law enforcement field, personal effectiveness of a personnel particularly police officers are influenced by set of ethics and leadership which encompasses set of principles and values that are recognized by the majority as a sound basis for the common good and includes integrity, respect, trust, fairness, transparency, and honesty (Villirilli, 2021). In addition, Kuligowski (2022) stated that it is demonstrating appropriate and thoughtful act of conduct inside and outside an organization, respecting ethical beliefs and values and being motivated by the dignity and rights of others wherein it creates positive work culture and improve organizational/institutional image and reputation. The idea of leadership is guaranteed and performed with a high standard of morality and values to avoid violently assert over a public order by an individual or a group of persons or inside the PNP organization itself Nabe (2020).

Subsequently, ethical leadership as defined by Kuligowski (2022) is the ability of ethical leaders to ensure ethical values are aligned across the organization, promote open communication, avoid biases, lead by example, willing to accept responsibility and admit mistakes. He then revealed that ethical leaders who display good values through their words and actions establish positive image to their subordinate which results to personal and team effectiveness.

Correspondingly, ethical leadership has always been related to as crucial role in law enforcement wherein it is defined as a multidimensional concept which has a broad range of values and behaviors expressed as socialized virtues which can be helpful in empowering others (Hay,2020). In fact, according to Rappaport as cited by Balcazar, Keys and Vryhof (2019) empowering others wherein its impact is shown on the performance, effectivity, efficiency, and productivity of individuals (Alshammari, Almutairi, Thuwaini, 2015).

Further, Hirsch (2020) emphasizes the significant impact of empowerment on employee's personal effectiveness, wherein it increases employee's autonomy, resources, independence, and accountability. She also added that the willingness of leaders to share power among the team results to achieving better results among the team and organization and influences the confidence, determination, and discipline among the members.

The study of Al- Ababneh et al., (2018), revealed that empowerment have positive effects on the personal effectiveness and service recovery performance. Moreover, the study found the full mediating effect of empowerment in the relationship between personal effectiveness and service recovery performance. This was also supported by Kazlaukaite, Buciuuniene, & Turauskas, 2018) wherein they mentioned that empowerment has a positive effect on employee's personal effectiveness to which it is seen and observed on their positive attitudes, behaviours and commitment in an organization.

Personal effectiveness is defined as the leader's ability in empowering their employees (Kouzes and Posner as cited by Menon 2015). He also added that leaders recognize the ability of the employees and provides employees with the tools and authority required to continuously their performance in order to achieve competent workforce. Moreover, empowerment is defined as the process of enhancing feeling of self-efficacy and impact on the personal effectiveness among organizational members through helping, achieving, and succeeding (Marghany, 2015).

In addition, Landry (2019), cited in her study that emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to understand and manage your own emotions, as well as recognize and influence the emotions of those around you. She also mentioned that it is a critical attribute for virtually all levels of criminal justice professionals since it is essential for sound moral development and social responsibility. In general, it has shown that emotional intelligence has a significant direct effect on personal effectiveness, performance, job satisfaction and caring climate.

Hence, personal effectiveness was not only influenced by empowerment it also influenced by emotional intelligence, Balamohan, Tech & Gomathi (2015) mentioned that emotional intelligence is found to be positively correlated with personal effectiveness and team performance. They also added that it acts as an important determinant in analyzing, modifying and channelizing one's behavior towards self-growth and personal effectiveness to which, it plays a crucial and significant role in guiding and enhancing one's behavior to perform efficiently and effectively. Moreover, they also stated that personal effectiveness depends on how well individual manage situations efficiently including intra/interpersonal conflicts that exists between them.

Furthermore, emotional intelligence has indirect effect on performance through job satisfaction and caring climate wherein leaders set tone of the organization, however, if they lack emotional intelligence, it could have more far-reaching consequences, resulting in lower personnel engagement (Sembering, Nimran, Astuti, & Utami, 2020).

In sum, it is the connectedness and interdependency that personal effectiveness is able to grow, mature, develop and find full expression. Furthermore, they also mentioned that each of these relationships has the potential to contribute to the personal development and effectiveness (Burnham & Ireson, 2012).

The researcher will attempt to explain personal effectiveness among PNP Non - commissioned officers in their workplace. In order to have a further explanation on the personal effectiveness and its relations to ethical leadership, empowerment and emotional intelligence, the researcher will anchor the study on the Self - Efficacy theory introduced by the Canadian psychologist, Albert Bandura (1970). The sense of personal effectiveness is derived from Bandura's theory of self - efficacy, according to which individuals develop and regulate beliefs or convictions about their abilities to make actions or beliefs. Self - efficacy contend that police officers have shaped their personal effectiveness through their belief, principles and attributes towards their work and professions.

In addition, self- efficacy or contextual or situational confidence, feelings of self - efficacy are "belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situation" (Bandura, 1986). This theory insists that police officers have attributes and beliefs which makes them grow, mature, develop and have the full expression of their personal effectiveness (Burnham & Ireson, 2012). Moreover, according to Bandura, of all our reflective capacities that govern our behaviors, emotions, ethics and motivations, the sense of self efficacy is the most powerful vector.

On the other hand, Landry (2019) cited in her study that emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to understand and manage your own emotions, as well as recognize and influence the emotions of those around you. The term was first coined in 1990 by researchers John Mayer and Peter Salovey but was later popularized by psychologist Daniel Goleman. In effect of the theory of emotional intelligence, high emotional intelligence leads to have a higher self - control and higher control of stress and mood of disorders (Goleman). Thus, emotional intelligence is a critical attribute for virtually all levels of police officers as it helps build relationship, reduce team stress, defuse conflict, improve job satisfaction, and develop personal effectiveness.

In a likely manner, this study is also anchored to the social learning theory by Albert Bandura (1977) which emphasizes the importance of observing, modelling and imitating the behaviors, attitudes and emotional intelligence of others. Social learning theory considers how both environment and cognitive factors influence human learning and behavior. This theory is relevant to this study as it is believed that non-commissioned police officers may learn from their superiors or from the Commissioned police officers through observing, internalizing, direct modelling of ethical leadership styles and empowerment approaches and may adopt those behaviors that will contribute to their personal effectiveness, or otherwise which are unethical behaviors and personal ineffectiveness.

Moreover, Philippines National Police claimed that they are aware and admitted to the existence of various issues and problems including spanning governance, corruption, unethical leadership and behavior, suicidal attempts by the police officers, police crimes committed by the police officers and national security threats which show lack of personal effectiveness. However, in recent years, police department across the country has still been facing intense public scrutiny despite its strenuous efforts for multiple level of changes, personnel training and development programs and institutional development (Mendoza et al., 2021).

In addition, lack of personal effectiveness of the police officers resulted to abuse of power that effect to increasing offense scenes of violence, human rights abuses, and internal institutional issues (Adame, Perea & Manibo, 2019) and worst this caused downward trend on public's confidence and trust on the police force (Mynenko, 2022).

Although pieces of evidence, various conclusions have drawn and recommendations have been provided in an effort to address emerging issues among PNP personal effectiveness, however, limited studies were published on the personal effectiveness among non-commissioned officers in the Philippine National Police particularly in Davao Region.

Therefore, it is in this context that the researcher is interested to determine whether the ethical leadership style, empowerment, and the level of emotional intelligence of the Police Commissioned officers can be used as equation model on personal effectiveness among non-commissioned officers of the PNP as this can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop action plans to improve PNP administration in Davao region. Moreover, the goal of this research is to significantly contribute cumulative evidence and literatures to body of research.

The purpose of this study is to determine which model in ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence of the PNP commissioned officers significantly influences the personal effectiveness among PNP non-commissioned officers.

Specifically, it seeks to achieve the following objectives:(1) to ascertain the level of Ethical Leadership of PNP Commissioned officers, (2) to evaluate the level of empowerment of PNP Commissioned officers, (3) to describe the Emotional Intelligence of PNP commissioned officers, (4) to assess the Personal Effectiveness of the PNP Non-commissioned officers, (5) to determine the significant relationships between Ethical Leadership and Personal Effectiveness, Empowerment and Personal Effectiveness, Emotional Intelligence and Personal Effectiveness (6) to determine if Ethical Leadership, empowerment, and Emotional Intelligence significantly influence personal effectiveness of PNP non-commissioned officers and (7) to determine the best fit model on the Personal Effectiveness among PNP non-commissioned officers.

This study will have the following null hypotheses which will be tested at 0.05 level of significance: 1. There is no significant relationship between: Ethical Leadership and Personal Effectiveness; Empowerment and Personal Effectiveness; Emotional Intelligence and Personal Effectiveness; 2. Ethical Leadership, Empowerment, and Emotional Intelligence dimension do not significantly influence the personal effectiveness among PNP non-commissioned officers; and there is no best fit model that predicts the personal effectiveness.

Leaders in the law enforcement agencies plays a significant role in determining the ethical orientation of their agency. Specifically, leaders must regard ethics, empowerment, and emotional intelligence as a key component of the agency's culture in which officers behave ethically, improved personal effectiveness and respects the rights of others. In fact, the public puts their trust in to law enforcement agencies as the law enforcement officers are placed in a position of authority. Thus, results of this study could help in developing and strengthening intervention programs, personnel build up and development programs and contributed new models and insights to be able to be produced highly enthusiastic future police leaders that will lead to the prosperity, stability and security of the community as a whole. This may also help eradicate old systems, thus, embracing planned changes in line with administration, supervision and control to enhance agency's public trusts and reputations.

Similarly, results of this are notably beneficial to the community, law enforcement, uniformed personnel, private sectors, criminology practitioners and to the succeeding researchers. Hence, the findings are significant in attaining more efficient administration, supervision and control in law enforcement agencies. In addition, the study that will be conducted will similarly help the private sectors to seek more economic activities as they feel safe and secured. Moreover, the uniformed personnel and criminologist practitioners could give them insights and realizations for better understanding of themselves and will further bring awareness about their present condition when it come to their personal effectiveness. Further, it could also provide them information on the effect and impact of leadership that will affect their personal growth, emotional maturity and career development. Finally, the succeeding researchers can use this study as reference and baseline data in conducting related study or for a further study with wider and comprehensive scope. Further, it could serve as literatures or with testing the validity of related findings.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework of this study shown in Figure 1 focuses on analysis of the path model and correlational relationship from the independent variables to dependent variables and observable variables. Furthermore, the model will present dependencies and relationships between dependent and independent variables. In this study, the independents variables are the ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the personal effectiveness. Moreover, each variable will be associated with observable variables.

This study is significant because this would help the entire department in assessing the current conditions of the PNP Commissioned and Non - commissioned officers in Davao Region. Moreover, being the lead agency of the government tasked with the promotion of human rights and law enforcement, it is important to improve and upgrade the administration, supervision, control capability, and personal effectiveness among PNP personnel in addressing contemporary challenges and improve public trust and reputations.

2. METHOD

Research Respondents

The researcher took 400 police officers of PNP Region XI also known as Davao Region comprises five provinces namely: Davao De Oro, Davao del Norte, Davao del Sur, Davao Oriental, and Davao Occidental. There are five cities in the entire region: Davao City, Digos, Mati, Panabo, Samal, and Tagum City. In addition, the region is located at the Southeastern portion of Mindanao. The region center is in Davao City wherein the Police Regional Office was also located. Furthermore, a Regional Training Center 11 or Philippine Public Safety College was also located in Davao City, Davao Del Sur. Additionally, the PNP PRO 11 has five (5) police districts, five (5) provinces and City of Davao under it.

A Scientific procedure was used to select the appropriate respondents for this study. Stratified random sampling technique that involves the division of a population into a smaller group known as strata was utilized to choose the respondents. The researcher selected the police officers who were assigned to the police provincial offices and the city police office of the PNP region XI. To achieve the maximum testing required, a total of not less than 400 respondents police officers were chosen by their Police Provincial Director to participate in the study and provided valuable data assessing and to meet the

objectives of this research. Therefore, obtaining a sample size of 400 was adequate and justifiable for path analysis as a subset for SEM. Since it is popularly believed in SEM that perhaps the research study population has a substantial level, the measure and correlation coefficient involved all data. In simulation studies for SEM, at least 400 assumptions or samples are required. For this study, the representative sample comprised police officers from each of the police provincial offices throughout the duration of study. SEM is a statistical modeling technique that sets forth reason-result relations among measured and unmeasured variables. SEM is a type of statistical modeling that shows how measured and unmeasured variables are related by cause and effect. SEM is used to analyzed data, multiple regression, factor, path, and covariance analysis. This technique is better employed for inferring facts from data and theories (Bhatta et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2017; Pearl, 2012). Path analysis was utilized in interpretation of data to determine the direct, indirect, and total relationship of independent to constant variables this methods used to discern and assess the effects of a set of variables acting on a specified outcome via multiple causal pathways and a precursor to and subset of structural equation modeling.

The study was done in Davao Region. Before being retrieved from their stations by the researcher, the respondents were given ample time to familiarize the questionnaire. The respondents can freely change their mind and does not require to participate. Unless they are willing personally, they can respond differently without repercussions for whatever reason they have. Only willing police officers in providing personal information and data were included during the survey and they were assured that any information given would be treated with utmost respect and confidentiality. Excluded in this research are non-uniformed personnel of the Philippine National Police in Region XI. Moreover, those questionnaires which are not answered and/or personally answered by the respondents were excluded. Further, those respondents who decided to withdraw during the study due to some reasons were allowed.

Research Materials and Instruments

The survey questionnaires were adopted from the following studies: The Ethical Leadership Self-Assessment Tool – Veterans Affairs (IntegratedEthics, 2017), Empowerment and Occupational Stress Of International Society For Performance Improvement Members (Marshall, 2002), Development Of The Emotional Intelligence Scale (Mehta & Singh, 2013), and Personal Effectiveness: A Case Study (Choudhary, 2016). The instrument was extracted and revised topics or item statements that are included and relevant to the study. This made it more appropriate for the respondents. Six specialists validated it in the domains of ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness to make the instrument more current and substantial.

After validating the survey questionnaires, pilot testing was done and completed. Cronbach alpha was measured to gauge the questionnaire's reliability. Generally, the alpha consistency coefficient of Cronbach was considered these falls between zero and one. It is considered that the greater the internal consistency of a specific scale's items, the closer Cronbach's alpha coefficient reaches to one (Simon & Choi, 2018).

The five gradations of variables with a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations are as follows: a range the mean of 4.20-5.00 would mean very high, which translates that ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness are always manifested, 3.40-4.19 would mean high, which means that ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness are often manifested; 2.60-3.39 means moderate, which means that the that ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness are sometimes manifested; 1.80-2.59 means the response is low which further explains that that ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness are rarely manifested and; a response of 1.00-1.79 means that that ethical leadership, empowerment, emotional intelligence, and personal effectiveness are rarely manifested.

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, non-experimental research making use of both descriptive and correlation research methods. A non-experimental design was included in research designs which the researcher describes a group or examined the relationship between pre-existing groups (Salkind, 2010). Descriptive - correlation technique described a certain phenomenon and peoples experienced it and determined whether a relationship exists among several variables at one point in time (Creswell, 2008). In addition, the study made use of the design that allows you to predict an outcome, such as the prediction that ability, demography, and quality of schooling can influence personal achievement and effectiveness (Anderson & Keith, 1997).

The data utilized in this study were collected using several processes. The first step was obtaining the UMERC – University of Mindanao's Ethics Review Committee certificate authorizing the research to be executed. Second, the researcher sent a

letter request to the offices concerned wherein the data is gathered. After that the questionnaires were produced, the floating and retrieval of the questionnaires followed. Afterwards, the data analysis steps were done by compiling and tabulating first the retrieved data and data processing and interpretation followed. Evaluating the results and interpreting them considering the purpose of the study.

The researcher gathered, measured, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted on the data using the following statistical tools: Mean, Regression analysis, Two - way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) and Path Analysis. Mean was used to determine the level of ethical leadership, describe the emotional intelligence and level of empowerment of the PNP Commissioned officers as well as in assessing the personal effectiveness of the PNP Non - Commissioned officers. The two-way multivariate analysis of variance (two-way MANOVA) was used to test the significant relationship between the ethical leadership and personal effectiveness, empowerment and personal effectiveness, and emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness. Furthermore, the GLM Multivariate procedure was then utilized to perform the two-way MANOVA test with Wilks' Lambda as the multivariate statistic. Regression Analysis was used to determine the significant influence of ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence to personal effectiveness of PNP Non - commissioned Officers. Finally, Path Analysis was used to investigate the direct effects of the Personal Effectiveness among PNP Non - commissioned officers.

In terms of ethical consideration, throughout the process, the study underwent a careful evaluation and full ethical standard set and required by the UMERC with the certification number UMERC-2023-217 complied including the research protocols, standards and ethics, procedure assessment and guidelines particularly in population management and data collection including voluntary participations, privacy and confidentiality of the respondents, informed consent process, permission from organization/location, conflict of interests and plagiarism. In the Informed Consent Process, the researcher's questionnaire was free of technical terms and understandable to the respondents of the study. The questionnaires were administered with the consent and support of the Professional Schools. No research questionnaires were distributed without permission from the authorized personnel and offices. In addition, all respondents were given the free-will to participate without any form of coercion or penalty. Further, the respondents' personal information that were required in the study will be kept in private and was treated with utmost confidentiality.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the study results and a discussion of the data.

Ethical Leadership of PNP

Shown in Table 1 are data on ethical leadership of PNP of Region XI, garnering an overall mean score of 4.17, classified as high, accompanied by a standard deviation of .556, indicating responses from the clustered respondents. This means that the ethical leadership of PNP of Region XI is high in level and considered evident.

The practicing ethical decision-making indicator got the highest mean of score of 4.18, described as high in level with standard deviation of .600, showing clustered answers from the respondents. This shows that the PNP officers are practicing high ethical decision making. Furthermore, the indicator communicated clear expectations for ethical practice garnered a mean score of 4.17, declared as high in level, accompanied by a standard deviation of .643, manifesting clustered reactions from the respondents. This shows that the PNP officers possess a high communicating clear expectation for ethical practice.

In addition, the indicator supporting local ethics program garnered a mean score of 4.17, declared as high in level, accompanied by a standard deviation of .554, manifesting clustered reactions from the respondents. This means that the PNP officers support local ethics program of the organization. The indicator demonstrating that the ethics is a priority indicator got a mean score of 4.16, described as a high level or strongly evident with a standard deviation of .619, showing clustered answers from the respondents. This shows that the PNP officers are highly demonstrating that ethics is a priority.

Table 1. Level of Ethical Leadership

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
demonstrating that ethics is a priority	4.16	.619	high
communicating clear expectations for ethical practice	4.17	.643	high
practicing ethical decision making	4.18	.600	high
supporting local ethics program	4.17	.654	high
Overall	4.17	.556	high

An indication that practicing ethical decision making in the results shows a high level which implies that PNP officers is guided by professional guidelines and organizational policies standards in making decisions and shows a simple process of orders to their subordinates in line with law enforcement code of ethics. In addition to the findings ethical values of leaders in the organization displayed good actions and words that establish positive image to their subordinates, which also results to personal and team effectiveness and ensure good ethical decision making and programs that willing to accept responsibilities and lead by examples. (Kuligowski, 2022)

Furthermore, the second highest mean score is an indicator that communicating clear expectations for ethical practice got 4.17, declared as high in level, with a standard deviation of .643, or oftentimes evident is best described as leaders in the police organizations have strong manifestation of giving clear and systematized ethical practice. The findings correspond the statement of Villrilli (2021), stating that a sound basis recognized by the majority for common good is the clear sets of principles and values that encompass integrity, respect, trust, fairness, transparency, and honesty in the organization.

Moreover, the indicator *supporting local ethics program* garnered a mean score of 4.17, declared as high in level, accompanied by a standard deviation of .554, manifesting the results is oftentimes evident. This means that PNP officers of region XI ensures that all activities aligned across the organization that promotes local ethics programs are supported. This statement anchors to the moral recovery program of the Philippine National Police that aims to encourage all its members and public servants to internalized that maintaining integrity in the service, honesty, and taking positive measures against unethical practices should be given prioritized and strengthen their Filipino values, culture, traditions, and putting God as the center in everything. An indication that demonstrating that the ethics is a priority is of high level or manifested as oftentimes evident means that the PNP of Region XI ensure that leaders in the police service possess a high average of ethical values and good working environment and relationship with their subordinates. In addition, ethics is essential part of democratic way of enforcing the law and must be given a priority since there is no person considered as someone above the law. The findings is supported by the idea of Nabe (2020), leadership is guaranteed and performed with a high standard of morality and values to avoid violence and assert public order to an individual or a group of persons, outside or inside the PNP organization.

Empowerment of PNP

Table 2 displays the level of the empowerment of PNP of Region XI, having an overall mean score of 4.22 labeled as very high with a standard deviation of .547, indicating clustered answers from the respondents. This means that the empowerment of the PNP of Region XI is of a very high level. With a mean score of 4.22, the indicator *trust* was determined very high, accompanied by a standard deviation of .620, indicating clustered reactions from the respondents.

This shows that PNP officers have a very high level of *trust* with a mean score of 4.22 and standard deviation of .620 with a descriptive level. labeled as very high the indicator *encouragement* garnered a mean score of 4.22 accompanying standard deviation of .574. This shows that PNP officers has a very high level of encouragement in the organization. Regarding *enablement*, the acquired mean score is 4.21, gauged very high with a standard deviation of .569, indicating clustered responses. This indicates that PNP has a very high level of enablement.

Table 2. Level of Empowerment

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Trust	4.22	.620	very high
enablement	4.21	.569	very high
encouragement	4.22	.574	very high
Overall	4.22	.547	very high

Empowerment of the PNP of Region XI is of a very high level. This means that PNP officers strongly manifested inspiration to their subordinates. Trust, as one of the indicators of empowerment, has very high and strong manifestation on firm belief that police officers are reliable, trusted, confident, and reliable. This coincides to the study of Hirsch (2020) that increasing employees' autonomy, resources, independence, and accountability is from the willingness of leaders to share power among the team lead to achieving better results among the team and organization and influences the confidence, determination, and discipline among members.

The indicator of encouragement which is found very high and always manifested. The findings best demonstrated that PNP officers highly give courage to their subordinates and focus and getting better, motivated, and performing duties. Committing to support and helping each other for attaining the objectives and services opted for its constituents. Menon

(2015) cited in his study, leaders recognize the ability of the employees and provides the tools and authority required to continue their performance to achieve competent workforce. Marghany (2015) added that enhancing feeling of self-efficacy and impact on personal effectiveness among organizational members through helping, achieving, and succeeding.

Furthermore, the indicator enablement gauged very high and strongly evident. This indicates that PNP officers of region XI concerned about whether their subordinates are creative and given support machinery to develop skills and able to perform the duties and responsibilities of a police officers. The study of Al-Ababneh et al., (2018) supported that service recovery performance has a positive effect. Moreover, the study also proved that empowerment and its good result can be seen and observed on the attitudes, behaviors, and commitment in an organization. Thus, enablement can be link to innovation that benefits changes and improvement in the police service Kazlaukaite et al., (2018).

Emotional Intelligence of PNP

Data presented in table 3 show results in emotional intelligence of PNP of Region XI, with an overall mean core of 4.21, described as a very high level and having a standard deviation of .503, indicating clustered responses from the respondents. This shows that the emotional intelligence of the PNP officers of Region XI is very high level. With a mean score of 4.35 and a standard deviation of .657, classified as clustered responses, the indicator self-awareness is very high. This means that it is evident at most times and indicates that police officers believe that capability to focus on yourself and knowing more about emotions, actions, and your own thoughts is significant.

The findings supported by statement of Landry (2019) that ability to understand and manage your own emotions, as well as recognize and influence the emotions of those around you is critical attribute for all levels of professionals since it is essential for sound moral development and social responsibility. In general, it shows a significant direct effect on individual effectiveness, performance, job satisfaction and caring climate.

Table 3. Level of Emotional Intelligence

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
self-awareness	4.35	.657	very high
emotional regulation	4.12	.571	high
self-management/motivation	4.23	.552	very high
social awareness	4.18	.536	high
social management skills	4.19	.542	high
emotional receptivity	4.19	.545	high
Overall	4.21	.503	very high

Moreover, the indicator *self-management/motivation* acquired a mean score of 4.23, described as very high in level with a standard deviation of .552, indicating clustered responses. This indicates that PNP officers of region XI are highly motivated with excellent self-managerial capabilities. The findings coincide the study of Sembering et. Al (2020) stated that indirect effect on performance through job satisfaction and caring climate wherein leaders set tone of the organization if they lack emotional intelligence which includes self-management and motivation could results in lower personnel engagement.

Also, the indicator *social management skills* garnered mean score is 4.19, labeled as high level with an accompanying standard deviation of .542, indicating clustered responses. This result shows PNP officers have highly developed and skilled on strategies that maintain and grow a social presence and cooperation in the police organization since the task of administrative team is responsible in society active participation campaign. This finding is supported by the statement of Florendo (2012) said the effectiveness of leaders is reflected of their managerial capabilities, particularly in the field of law enforcement.

Furthermore, with a mean score of 4.19, with a standard deviation of .545, classified as clustered responses from the respondents, the indicator emotional receptivity is labeled high. This shows that the PNP officers' attentiveness is of a high level. The respondent labeled their superior as a person with genuine interest, active listener, always pays attention to their needs, and listens to what they say. The willingness of police officers to receive and accept ideas is of a significant point.

While emotional regulation garnered a mean score of 4.12, classified as high in level with a standard deviation of .571, showing responses clustered from the respondents. The emotional regulation domain is labeled as high by the PNP officers declaring that they have a great sense of self-control over matters and respond to demands of workload and experiences that is sufficiently flexible and socially tolerable. Balamohan et. Al. (2015) mentioned that the important determinant in analyzing, modifying, and channeling one's behavior to perform efficiently and effectively depend on how well individuals manage situations efficiently including intra/interpersonal conflicts that exists among them.

Regarding social awareness, the respondents gauged such indicators as high in level with a mean score of 4.18 labeled as high level and having a standard deviation of .536, indicating clustered responses from the respondents. The result showed that PNP officers gave highly understand the social and ethical norms including ability to recognize diverse backgrounds and cultures of its subordinates. The claim of these results is supported by the concept of social contract that the police officers are expected to conduct themselves at the maximum levels of integrity and must obey rules and laws of society and clearly manifested that respect and protection of the rights of citizens is the utmost priority (Nabe, 2020).

Personal Effectiveness of PNP

Shown in Table 4 is the level of personal effectiveness of PNP of Region XI with an overall mean score of 4.05, described as high, accompanied by a standard deviation of .575, classified as clustered responses from the study respondents. The results described that the PNP Officers in region XI are highly effective personally. They are able to grow, mature, and find full expression. Burnham and Ireson (2012) mentioned that personal development and effectiveness contribute to greatest potential, connectedness, and interdependence of individuals.

Table 4. Level of Personal Effectiveness

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Overall	4.05	.575	High

Correlation Analysis of Ethical Leadership and Personal Effectiveness among Police Commissioned Officers of PNP of Region XI

Table 5 shows the correlation analysis of ethical leadership and personal effectiveness of PNP of Region XI. All the indicators of the dependent variable, ethical leadership, namely, demonstrating that the ethics is a priority, communicating clear expectations for ethical practice, practicing ethical decision making, and supporting local ethics program, are correlated with the independent variable of personal effectiveness (p-value=0.000<0.001).

Overall computation manifested an r-value of 0.609, indicating high correlation, and a p-value of 0.000, which is lesser than the significance level of 0.01. The result showed a significant relationship and thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between leadership behavior and personal effectiveness among PNP of Region XI.

The dependent variable and personal effectiveness are correlated with all the indicators of the first independent variable, leadership behavior. The overall result showed a significant relationship and thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. This means there was a significant relationship between ethical leadership and personal effectiveness among PNP of Region XI. This also implies that the determination of the significant relationship was the indication of regression analysis between the two variables.

Table 5. Correlation Analysis of Ethical Leadership and Personal Effectiveness among Police Commissioned Officers

Ethical Leadership	Personal Effectiveness
demonstrating that the ethics is a priority	.520** (.000)
communicating clear expectations for ethical practice	.525** (.000)
practicing ethical decision making	.571** (.000)
supporting local ethics program	.538** (.000)
Overall	.609** (.000)

***p<0.01

Correlation Analysis of Empowerment and Personal Effectiveness among Police Commissioned Officers

Table 6 displays the correlation analysis of the empowerment and personal effectiveness of PNP of Region XI. The dependent variable, personal effectiveness, is known to be correlated with all the indicators of the second independent variable, empowerment, namely trust, enablement, and encouragement (p-value=0.000<0.001).

Overall computation manifested the computed r-value of 0.6.26, indicating a high correlation. At the same time, the p-value of 0.000 is lower when compared with the level of significance of 0.01, showing a significant relationship between the two

variables resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. It could be declared, therefore, that there is a significant relationship between the empowerment and personal effectiveness among PNP of Region XI.

The dependent variable, personal effectiveness, are disclosed to be correlated with all the indicators of the second independent variable empowerment. Overall computation showed a significant relationship between the two variables resulting in rejecting the null hypothesis. It means that there was a significant relationship between the empowerment and personal effectiveness among PNP of Region XI. Similarly, this also implies that the determination of the significant relationship indicated regression analysis between the two variables.

Table 6. Correlation analysis of empowerment and personal effectiveness among police commissioned officers

Empowerment	Personal Effectiveness
Trust	.561** (.000)
enablement	.577** (.000)
encouragement	.611** (.000)
Overall	.626** (.000)

***p<0.01

Correlation Analysis of Emotional Intelligence and Personal Effectiveness among Police Commissioned Officers of PNP of Region XI

Table 6 displays the correlation analysis of emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness of PNP of Region XI. The dependent variable personal effectiveness is showed to be correlated with all the indicators of the third independent variable, emotional intelligence, namely self-awareness, emotional regulation, self-management/motivation, social awareness, social awareness, social management skills, and emotional receptivity (P-value = 0.000<0.01).

Overall, the computation disclosed an r-value of 0.714, manifesting a high level of correlation. In equivalence, the p-value yielded 0.000, which is lesser when compared with the level of significance of 0.01, showing a significant relationship. It can be declared, therefore, the rejection of the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness.

The dependent variable, personal effectiveness, is disclosed to be correlated with all the indicators of the third independent variable, emotional intelligence. Overall, the computation showed a significant relationship, thereby:

Table 7. Correlation analysis of emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness among police commissioned officers

Emotional Intelligence	Personal Effectiveness
self-awareness	.506** (.000)
emotional regulation	.611** (.000)
self-management/motivation	.657** (.000)
social awareness	.706** (.000)
social management skills	.646** (.000)
emotional receptivity	.673** (.000)
Overall	.714** (.000)

***p<0.01

rejecting the null hypothesis, which means a significant relationship exists between emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness. Moreover, this also implies that the determination of the significant relationship indicated regression analysis between the two variables.

Significant Influence of Ethical Leadership, Empowerment, and Emotional Intelligence, and towards Personal Effectiveness of PNP

Table 8 manifests the significant influence of the independent variables towards personal effectiveness of PNP of Region XI with a computed F-value of 140.674, R-value of .517, the adjusted R-value of .513, and p-value of .000 showing to be lower compared to a .05 level of significance. It is evident, therefore, that the independent variables influence personal effectiveness. The data shows that the adjusted R2 value of .513 emphasizes that independent variables influence personal effectiveness by 51.3%. The difference of 48.7% is a characteristic not included in the present study.

Table 8. Regression analysis of ethical leadership, emotional intelligence, and emotional intelligence as explanatory variables of personal effectiveness among police commissioned officers

Independent Variables	B	S.E.	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.539	.173		3.123	.002
ethical leadership	.163	.070	.158	2.344	.020*
Empowerment	-.067	.087	-.064	-.771	.441 ^{ns}
emotional intelligence	.739	.081	.645	9.159	.000**

F = 140.674, p < 0.01

R² = 0.517

ΔR² = 0.513

The particulars on the findings of the influence of independent variables on personal effectiveness among PNP of Region XI pointed out that ethical leadership had standardized and unstandardized coefficients of .163 and .158, t-value of 2.344 and p-value of .000 (Significant); empowerment had standardized and unstandardized coefficients of -.067 and -.064, with t-value of -.771 and p-value of .441 (Not Significant); emotional intelligence had standardized and unstandardized coefficients of .739 and .645, t-value of 9.159 and p-value of .000 (Significant).

It was apparent that the independent variables, namely ethical leadership and emotional intelligence, significantly influenced personal effectiveness. While empowerment is not significantly influencing the independent variables. Thus, the independent variables influence personal effectiveness by 51.3%. The difference of 48.7% is a characteristic not included in the present study.

Path analysis showing the significance of the effect of exogenous variables.

Results shown below revealed that empowerment (EMPOWER) has no direct effect on personal effectiveness (EFFECTI). It has for emotional intelligence (INTEL) and ethical leaderships (ETHLEAD). The most popular means to determine path coefficients estimates is to do the next series of regression analyses. In the first step, regression was used to predict empowerment (EMPOWER) from ethical leadership (ETHLEAD). The result in table 9 and Figure 2 yielded an estimate of .834 and a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating that the effect of ETHLEAD to EMPOWER is statistically significant.

Figure 2. Conceptual model showing the hypothesized paths of direct and indirect effects of ethical leadership (ETHLEAD), empowerment (EMPOWER), and emotional intelligence (INTEL) on personal effectiveness (EFFECTI)

Table 9. Results of the path analysis showing the significance of the effect of exogenous variables towards

Path	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Notes on Path
EMPOWER <--- ETHLEAD	.834	.026	31.897	<.001	Significant
INTEL <--- EMPOWER	.649	.043	15.052	<.001	Significant
INTEL <--- ETHLEAD	.167	.042	3.928	<.001	Significant
EFFECTI <--- EMPOWER	-.067	.086	-.772	.440 ^{ns}	Insignificant
EFFECTI <--- INTEL	.738	.080	9.188	<.001	Significant
EFFECTI <--- ETHLEAD	.164	.069	2.373	.018	Significant

In the second step, a regression was also performed to predict emotional intelligence (INTEL) from empowerment (EMPOWER). As seen in table 9 and Figure 2, the result of this regression revealed an estimate of .649 and a p-value of less than 0.001 which indicates statistically significant. In the next step, the same statistical treatment was used to predict the emotional intelligence (INTEL) from ethical leadership (ETHLEAD). The result in table 9 and figure 2 yielded an estimate of .167 and p-value of less than 0.001, indicating that the effect of ETHLEAD on INTEL is scientifically significant. The same statistical treatment was performed on personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) form Empowerment (EMPOWER). This time as shown in table 9 and figure 2, the estimate of -.067 and a p-value of .440, indicate statistically insignificant.

Furthermore, a regression was also used to predict personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) from emotional intelligence (INTEL). The result yielded an estimate of .738 and p-value of less than 0.001 which indicates scientifically significant. Lastly, the same regression was also performed to predict the personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) from ethical leadership (ETHLEAD). The result as shown in table 9 and figure 2 has estimate of .164 and a p-value of less than 0.001 that signify statistically significant.

Direct and Indirect Effects

This study’s hypothesized and conceptualized models were formulated and tested. The variables were scrutinized and conducted critical analysis to provide an optimum result on the given data. The models generated in this study were supported with theories, other researches, and the variables with interval or ratio data were included in the formulation of models.

Table 10 shows the direct effect sizes of the path model, which is empowerment (EMPOWER) has a direct effect size of .834 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD), furthermore emotional intelligence (INTEL) has a direct effect size of .167 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD) and .649 direct effect size for empowerment (EMPOWER). The dependent variable personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) has a direct effect size of .164 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD) and .738 for emotional intelligence (INTEL) which indicates scientifically significant. While -.067 for empowerment that signifies scientifically insignificant.

Table 10. Direct effect sizes of the path model

	ETHLEAD	EMPOWER	INTEL
EMPOWER	.834	-	-
INTEL	.167	.649	-
EFFECTI	.164	-.067	.738

Figure 3. Final model showing the significant and insignificant paths of hypothesized influence of variables

Table 11 below presented indirect effect sizes of path models as shown in Figure 3. The variable emotional intelligence (INTEL) has indirect effect size of .541 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD). The personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) has .466 indirect effect for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD) and indirect effect size of path model of .479 for empowerment (EMPOWER) as shown in Figure 3 above.

Table 11. Indirect effect sizes of the path model

	ETHLEAD	EMPOWER	INTEL
EMPOWER	-	-	-
INTEL	.541	-	-
EFFECTI	.466	.479	-

Table 12 below shows the total effect sizes of the path model. The empowerment (EMPOWER) has a total effect of .834 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD). The emotional intelligence (INTEL) has a total effect size of path model of .708 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD) and total effect size of .649 for empowerment (EMPOWER). Lastly, dependent variable personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) has a total effect size of .631 for ethical leadership (ETHLEAD), and total effect size of .412 for empowerment (EMPOWER) and a total effect size of .738 for emotional intelligence (INTEL).

Table 12. Total effect sizes of the path model

	ETHLEAD	EMPOWER	INTEL
EMPOWER	.834	-	-
INTEL	.708	.649	-
EFFECTI	.631	.412	.738

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the level of Ethical Leadership of PNP Commissioned officers of Region XI is high particularly in practicing ethical decision making, communicating clear expectations for ethical practice, and supporting ethical ethics program. Nevertheless, while their ethical leadership is commendable, it is apparent that there is still a room for improvement warranting further enhancement such as demonstrating that the ethics is a priority, which may be addressed by the PNP Commissioned Officers by promoting ethical behavior and always being a good model, as well as engaging with subordinates and learning from mistakes, if any.

For the second objective, the level of empowerment of PNP Commissioned officers of PNP in Davao Region is very high mainly in trust, and encouragement. While enablement can be developed by giving right approach, training, and fostering a culture of open communication between PNP Commissioned Officers and PNP Non-Commissioned Officers in Region XI.

The level of Emotional Intelligence of PNP commissioned officers described as very high for self-awareness and self-management/motivation and high level for social management skills, social awareness, and social awareness. While the emotional regulations labeled as high this indicator also needs enhancement by engaging in positive environment and emotions. The PNP Commissioned Officers must be mindful in acceptance of emotions and keep themselves away from source of negative sentiments.

For the dependent variable, the level of Personal Effectiveness of the PNP Non-commissioned officers is high. However, even though the result is admirable advancement in Personal Effectiveness of the PNP Non-Commissioned Officers in Region XI is vital. This may be improve through specialized training, improved working relationships with colleagues and supervisors, manage multiple tasks, and strengthen their involvement in the community.

For the regression analysis results the ethical leadership and emotional intelligence significantly influence the personal effectiveness. While empowerment does not significantly influence the personal effectiveness. This means that as ethical leadership and emotional intelligence increase, personal effectiveness also increases. However, empowerment on the other hand, do not necessarily affect the personal effectiveness. It is therefore suggested that, cultivating ethical leadership within PNP organization can improve the personal effectiveness among police officers. Consequently, it is recommended that trainings and intervention programs must be conducted to promote and develop individual leadership skills and considered ethics as a main form of reorganization programs in the PNP organization. Considering this area, it will provide police officers with knowledge and skills needed to boost personal effectiveness.

After determining best causal model it is evident that performing the path analysis is the finest one, the results revealed that empowerment (EMPOWER) has no direct effect on personal effectiveness (EFFECTI) as the study's predictor and criterion variable. Thus, empowerment does not remove nor significantly reduce the relationship of PNP officer empowerment of Region XI to the personal effectiveness. On the other hand, ethical leadership (ETHLEAD) and Emotional Intelligence thus.

Therefore, law enforcement agencies must strive to extend a profound insight and give importance to police officers individual effectiveness. Police organizations should invest in personal effectiveness of each police officer beyond mere acknowledgement and recognitions. Trainings and partnership with the community and other law enforcement agencies to improve leadership capabilities of police officers will not only improve personal effectiveness but also the performance of PNP as a national organization.

Furthermore, it is also recommended that future research should continue exploring further factors and variables that impact the improvement of personal effectiveness and consider probable mediating mechanisms to gain deeper understanding of this concept within the context of the PNP and other law enforcement agencies and organizations. In enhancing and expanding our expertise and knowledge in this area. We can extend strategies and intervention programs to foster a high and greater police effectiveness and provide excellent services to the constituents.

In addition to the recommendations above, since the PNP PRO XI – Davao region has a positive result for this study of personal effectiveness with ethical leadership, empowerment, and emotional intelligence criteria as variable, it is evident that this study can be utilized by other Police Regional Office in the country and set that PRO XI – Davao region as a model police regional office since this can also support the recent accomplishment received by the office as Best Police Regional Office in the country among the 17 PROs during the 122nd Police Service Anniversary according to Philippine News Agency on August 9, 2023.

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